

MultiXscale

Plan for the design of a portable test suite

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	Contributors:	Kenneth Hoste (Ghent University), Lara Peeters (Ghent University)
	Reviewed by:	Alan O'Cais (University of Barcelona)
	Approved by:	Matej Praprotnik (National Institute of Chemistry)

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¹caspar.vanleeuwen@surf.nl

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Executive Summary

This report outlines a plan for the development of a portable test suite, which can be used to verify the quality of the European Environment for Scientific Software Installations (EESSI) shared software stack.

In Section 2 we discuss HPC testing frameworks, different types and levels of testing (and how these apply to testing the EESSI shared software stack), and the Continuous Integration (CI) workflow and periodic testing of the shared software stack. A portable test suite is being developed for the shared software stack using the ReFrame High Performance Computing (HPC) testing framework. Testing of the shared software stack is being done as part of the CI workflow in two stages. First, single node tests on a build node (integration testing), right after building new software. Second, after deployment of the new software to a staging environment, multi-node tests will be run (system testing). Additionally, periodic testing will be performed on various systems. This allows for identifying regressions that occur due to changes that are outside of the scope the shared software stack (e.g., changes to the host system).

In Section 3 we discuss how a typical ReFrame test is set up, and why that is not portable. We propose several concrete adjustments to make these tests portable. The key idea is to avoid using any system-specific information in the tests, and to rely on the ReFrame configuration file to provide such system-specific information. For example, traditionally a test explicitly defines the number of tasks by matching it with the number of CPU cores in a system to run on a full system. We reverse this process by defining that a test should run on a full node, and the task count is then determined *at run time* based on the amount of available cores that is configured in the ReFrame configuration file. The code used to achieve these kind of portability adaptations forms a set of utilities, *hook functions*, and *constants* that are an integral part of the portable test suite. They are easily reusable in future tests, to limit the effort required for developing of additional portable tests.

In Section 4 we present a proof of concept for a portable test, developed using the strategies proposed in Section 3. GROMACS was selected as a test case, due to its highly versatility: it runs at a wide range of scales, hardware, etc. The GROMACS test developed in this proof of concept serves as a blueprint for future portable tests. Furthermore, we ran this test on four different clusters: two EuroHPC JU clusters, a cluster operated by one of the MultiXscale partners, and a virtual Slurm cluster in AWS. Results from these runs demonstrate both the portability, as well as the test's capability to identify system-specific issues.

This report presents a plan for the further development of the portable test suite that can be used for testing the shared software stack. Testing will be done both in a CI workflow, as well as periodically. Next steps are to create a portable solution for performance reference data, and to expand the coverage of the test suite by adding tests for more software.

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable describes our plan for designing and developing a portable test suite. It presents the lessons learned so far in Task 1.3 - "Design and creation of a software test suite and facilitating CI for software developers" - and translates these into a plan for the development of a portable test suite for the shared software stack.

1.2 Target audience of the deliverable

The plan for the design of a portable test suite in this report is targeted at readers with experience in HPC system support, particularly in the context of maintaining and testing software stacks (or specific applications) for HPC infrastructure.

1.3 Motivation for portable test suite

Quality assurance is essential for a software stack that will be used by many users and/or on very large HPC systems. This is because in these cases, if software runs incorrectly or with subpar performance, the amount of resources that are potentially wasted are particularly large.

HPC sites typically maintain a central software stack that is made available to end users via environment modules [1]. Many sites strive to create tests for these software stacks to validate the correct functionality and performance, and spot any regressions caused by system maintenance (e.g. upgrading of Operating System (OS), hardware, drivers, etc). However, in reality only a limited number of sites have sufficient staff to spend the effort of setting up such test suites, and even then, the available tests often only have limited coverage of the central software stack. These tests often contain a lot of site-specific aspects, which makes it hard to share the burden of developing and maintaining such test suites between HPC sites, despite significant overlap between the site-specific central software stacks.

The EESSI shared software stack presents both a challenge and an opportunity in this respect. The opportunity is that, since EESSI provides one common software stack across systems, it takes away one of the variables in which sites normally differ: the software stack itself (which software is available, which versions, the user interface to access it, etc.). The additional challenge is that EESSI aims to support a wide variety of systems, and thus also needs to be *tested* on a variety of systems. This implies that any form of system-specific choice should be avoided when defining a test, or at the very least postponed to a run-time decision.

Since this is a deviation from the standard practice in HPC software testing, a fair amount of experimentation and planning is required. Such a plan is formalized in the form of this deliverable.

2 Software testing on HPC systems

2.1 HPC testing frameworks

HPC systems are complex machines:

- Software is typically provided through environment modules;
- Running a software test requires creating a job allocation, running the test, and verifying the result;
- The system might be heterogeneous, and different tests might require different resources.

To deal with this complexity, a dedicated framework is essential. A number of such frameworks exists, for example, pavilion2 [2], buildtest [3], JUBE [4] and ReFrame [5].

Typically, these frameworks provide a number of features, such as

- Scheduling tests as jobs, and keeping track of job status;
- Abstraction from the batch system, so that testing code is independent from the specific batch system that will be used to execute it;
- Interaction with the environment modules tool;
- An (optional) compilation step that is part of the test;
- Checking for patterns in the output to determine whether or not a test was run correctly;
- Extracting performance results from the test output or results (optional);

In MultiXscale, several project partners have prior experience in developing tests using ReFrame, which to the best of our knowledge is the most widely used tool for software testing in the HPC community. In addition, it is implemented in Python, which is ubiquitous in the domain of computational science, and provides a lot of flexibility.

Moreover, CSCS is one of the key sites developing ReFrame, and they have formally expressed their support for the MultiXscale Centre of Excellence (CoE) through a Letter of Expression of Support. This presents us with a unique opportunity to collaborate with the ReFrame developers on features that benefit development of the portable test suite.

These key arguments make ReFrame the tool of choice for developing the portable test suite as part of the MultiXscale project.

2.2 Levels and types of testing

There are several levels of testing:

- Unit testing
- Integration testing
- System testing

Note that these levels of testing are hierarchical, where unit tests are the lowest level in the hierarchy, and system tests the highest: if a unit tests fails, there is no point to run integration or system tests. Similarly, if an integration test fails, system tests should not be run.

Then, there are also several types of tests:

- Smoke tests
- Regression tests
- Functional tests
- Performance tests

Definitions for these levels of testing and types of tests can be quite abstract. In this report, we will define how these translate to testing of the shared software stack. We will also define which of these testing levels and test types are intended to be covered by the portable test suite, and which are not (yet).

Note that the testing levels and test types are orthogonal to each other: for example, functional tests can be run at the unit testing level, but also at the system testing level.

2.2.1 Unit testing

In unit testing, the focus lies on evaluating particular components of a software project [6]. Unit tests are usually meant to be executed after building the software, but before installing it. Typically, a command like `make check` is used to run the unit test suite of a particular software project.

EasyBuild [7], which is used to install the shared software stack in the MultiXscale project, enables running a test step as part of the installation process. Not all software provides unit tests, but if software comes with a unit test suite, the convention in the EasyBuild community is to run these unit tests as a part of the installation procedure. Since running the unit tests is part of the installation procedure, it means they are typically run at installation time *only*.

2.2.2 Integration testing

Integration testing typically refer to tests that cover the combination of multiple software projects [8]. A test running an end-user application (e.g. GROMACS) on the build node, right before deploying it in the shared software stack is an example of what could be considered integration testing. Such a test would check the functionality and performance of the software that was just installed, including all the dependencies it was built against.

Testing the software on another host OS than was used during the build can also be done during integration testing. We will build experience before we decide if testing on another host OS provides sufficient additional information to justify the increased complexity for integration testing of the shared software stack.

2.2.3 System testing

System testing is testing conducted on a complete integrated system, to evaluate the system's compliance with its specified requirements [9]. In the context of the shared software stack, these requirements are that the end-user applications that are provided not only function on the system they were built on, but on *any* system, provided that it has an OS, CPU architecture, interconnect, and potentially accelerators (GPUs), that are supported.

System tests can use the same test cases as the integration tests, albeit in a more heterogeneous context. For example, several variations of the same test may be run:

- At different scales (e.g. single core, partial node, full node, multiple nodes);
- On different hardware configurations (e.g. on CPU-only or GPU nodes);
- On systems with different configurations (OS, system software versions, etc.);
- Using different version of the software;
- With different use cases, which may use different features of the software being tested.

This can result in a large amount of test "variants". As such, the aim is to try to limit run time of these tests to a few minutes. Also, it should be easy to run only a subset of all available tests, e.g. only single node, or only GPU tests, depending on the goal of the user of the portable test suite.

2.2.4 Smoke tests

Smoke tests [10] are very lightweight tests that are meant to quickly check if software is completely broken. Typical examples are just checking if a binary runs by trying to run it with a `--version` or `--help` argument, or check if certain files or directories are present. EasyBuild already defines such smoke tests [11] as a part of the "sanity check" step that is performed as a part of a software installation procedure.

Since smoke tests are an integral part of EasyBuild, they are already run right after installation of the software. We plan to implement a generic ReFrame test that triggers EasyBuild to re-run (only) the sanity check step. Currently, sanity checks in EasyBuild are sometimes not designed to be used this way, and hence we will have to evaluate whether this is a feasible approach. The big advantage is that these sanity checks are very light, so they can be run very regularly without consuming too much resources.

2.2.5 Regression tests

Regression tests [12] check if there are any regressions in a system. These can be both functional regressions (i.e., something is not working anymore, while it was before), or performance regressions (i.e., something is working, but requires significantly more time than before). One example of a regression in the context of the shared software stack could be a performance degradation after rebuilding particular software (or one of its dependencies). Another example would be a change in system drivers on the host system that causes a decrease in performance for a particular software application.

Regression tests can be used when there are known system changes (such as updating software), but it is also common to run regression tests on a periodic schedule. The latter is essentially a proactive way of monitoring the performance of the system as a whole. Periodic testing can help catch regressions that are not triggered by changes to the shared software stack itself. The example of a regression being caused by an update of system drivers demonstrates this: this update is outside of the control of the shared software stack, but the combination of a certain system driver version with software included in the shared software stack may still cause a performance decrease. Detecting this can be done through periodic regression testing.

2.2.6 Functional tests

Functional tests are a type of black-box testing [13]. It involves providing an input to a software application and examining if the result produced is as expected, without considering the internal program application structure. In the context of the portable test suite, all ReFrame based tests will test functionality. ReFrame requires the test programmer to specify a so-called *sanity pattern*, which is the expected outcome of the application if the program ran correctly. It is up to the programmer of the test to decide what makes most sense to use as sanity pattern, and it could be as simple as verifying that the program did not print any errors. More specific sanity patterns could require a particular numerical value in the test result to be in a certain range.

2.2.7 Performance tests

In performance tests, the performance of a software application is of main interest. A lot of scientific software applications report some kind of performance numbers (e.g., GROMACS reports how many nanoseconds of a molecular structure can be simulated in a day of compute time). Capturing this performance number from the output and validating it against some form of reference is referred to as performance testing.

2.3 Overview of testing for the shared software stack

Software in the shared software stack will get tested according to two schedules:

- Upon deployment, as part of a CI workflow;
- At regular intervals, e.g. daily or weekly.

2.3.1 CI workflow

Figure 1: Continuous integration (CI) workflow used when creating shared software stack

The Continuous Integration (CI) workflow used in the shared software stack is displayed in Figure 1. During the build, as part of the installation procedure, smoke tests and unit tests are typically already run. After the build, the relevant parts of the portable test suite will be run as part of integration testing. Initially, this will include single node test cases for selected applications. This may be refined later to cover only the subset of applications expected to be affected by the changes in that specific build (to save computational resources).

After (successful) integration testing, the additional software that was built will be deployed to a staging environment, where system testing will be performed, including multi-node tests for selected software applications included in the shared software stack.

Finally, after successful system testing, the builds are effectively deployed to the shared software repository.

2.3.2 Periodic testing

Periodic runs of the portable test suite have already been set up on various systems, including the Euro High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC JU) systems Vega and Karolina, and a Slurm cluster within a commercial cloud environment (such as Amazon Web Services (AWS)) that is also used to build software for the EESSI shared

software stack. These periodic runs of the portable test suite are meant to identify regressions that may be related to changes outside of the CI workflow. For example, system-specific changes which could cause particular software to be broken or run significantly slower than before *on that specific system*.

If multiple use cases are available for a given application, testing will be limited to a specific use case during periodic testing, to limit computational cost. Furthermore, we will regularly revisit the total computational costs of these periodic tests depending on the test suite size and frequency of the periodic runs.

3 Challenges in writing portable tests - and how we plan to overcome them

3.1 Anatomy of a typical ReFrame test

ReFrame aims to describe tests in a declarative way. Users implement their test in Python by inheriting from a generic ReFrame Python class, and specify class variables and/or instance variables to declare what their test should do.

Examples of typical variables that will be defined in a ReFrame test implementation are:

- `executable`: the executable to be run;
- `executable_opts`: the options to be passed to the executable
- `time_limit`: the time limit for the test job;
- `valid_systems`: a list of systems, as configured in the ReFrame configuration file, on which this test can be run;
- `valid_prog_environs`: valid programming environments, as specified in the ReFrame configuration file, in which this test can be run;
- `modules`: modules to be loaded before running the test;
- `num_tasks`: number of tasks / processes;
- `num_cpus_per_task`: number of CPU cores per task;
- `num_gpus_per_node`: number of GPUs per node;
- `sanity_pattern`: a pattern to use for verifying the test result;
- `performance_pattern`: a pattern to use for extracting a performance metric;
- `references`: reference performance values used to check for performance regressions;

From this list, it is immediately clear that some of these are specific to the test and independent of the system on which they are run (such as `executable`, `sanity_pattern`, etc.), while others are system specific to varying degrees (such as `num_tasks`, `valid_systems`, and `references`).

In an attempt to make this more generic, the ReFrame project developed the ReFrame Test Library [14], which was aimed to contain the generalizable part of tests. This reduced the effort needed for sites to develop their own implementation of these tests: they can now use class inheritance to inherit the generalizable part of a test, and only specify the system specific part in the child class (see for example CSCS's own ReFrame test suite [15]). Nevertheless, it still requires a significant implementation effort, since a site-specific child class needs to be defined for *each* of these tests. If the goal is specifically to have a large test suite that covers a lot of software, this effort can be (very) substantial.

For the portable test suite that will be used for testing the shared software stack, that is a deal breaker. A typical end user of the shared software stack should be able to run the portable test suite with *minimal* effort, in order to validate that the provided software installations work as expected on their system. Requiring to implement a subclass for all the tests in the portable test suite, based on their system specific details, is considered to demand an unreasonable amount of effort.

3.2 Separating test-specific and system-specific information

In this section, we will discuss the proposed approach in order to separate test-specific and system-specific information even further. The goal is that system-specific information is limited to one single file: the ReFrame configuration file. This is the only file that the end user will then have to create specifically for their system, in order to run the test suite.

Any system-specific aspects that were typically hard-coded in the test class, are deferred to run-time decisions based on information provided by the ReFrame configuration file (and the module environment). We will discuss the most important ones below.

3.2.1 Valid systems

Traditionally, specifying the `valid_systems` variable was a way of ensuring that the test was only run on hardware that was capable of running it. For example, a site would list only its GPU partitions in a test that requires GPUs to run.

To improve test portability, we suggest that a test should not define `valid_systems` (as that assumes the implementer of the test knows the specifics of the hardware in those systems), but instead specify the *requirements* that the test

has [16]. Support for this was implemented in ReFrame 3.11 (released April 2022) through features and extras [17]. With this, tests can, e.g., declare that they are only valid for partitions that provide GPUs (here, GPUs is a "feature") or even more specifically, that provide *NVIDIA* GPUs (here, the brand name is an "extra").

3.2.2 Valid programming environments

A programming environment is determined by which compilers are used, which (environment) modules need to be loaded for that, which corresponding environment values (like `CC`, `CXX`) are defined, etc. The `valid_prog_environs` variable is normally used in tests that compile some code before they run a test.

Although such tests could be integrated in the portable test suite, they are not our primary focus, which is to test functionality of *existing* software in the shared software stack. Nevertheless, if we want to include tests that need to be compiled first, the portability of such tests is a relatively trivial addition. The advantage of the shared software stack is that it creates a homogeneous software environment across systems, and thus the exact same program environments are present and valid anywhere.

3.2.3 Available environment modules

Rather than hard-coding names of environment modules in a test, the portable test suite will *discover* which relevant modules are available at run time. Again, the fact that the software environment is homogeneous across systems is an advantage: we know the module naming scheme, and can just search for the right patterns in order to find relevant modules. A `find_modules` function was defined as part of the portable test suite, which is used for module discovery. It is up to the implementer of a particular test to define the correct search pattern to discover all relevant modules.

3.2.4 Number of tasks, CPUs, and GPUs

The number of tasks is something of a grey area: it can be test specific, or system specific. For example, a network ping-pong test *always* involves exactly two tasks. However, for many ReFrame tests that test parallel codes, the traditional approach would be to define the `num_tasks` variable to match the available hardware. For example: setting `num_tasks` equal to the core count for pure Message Passing Interface (MPI) software on CPU nodes, or equal to the GPU count when testing software on GPU nodes. In these cases, the value of the `num_tasks` variable is system specific. Similar arguments can generally be made for the value of the `cpus_per_task` and `gpus_per_node` variables.

We plan to generalize this common pattern for test implementations in the portable test suite. We define fixed scales (e.g. single core, two core, quarter node, half node, single node, two nodes, etc.) at which the tests will be generated by ReFrame by default. Test implementers can limit the relevant scales when a test specific task count is applicable (for example with ping-pong tests). We will define standard functions that set `num_tasks`, `cpus_per_task`, and (if applicable) `gpus_per_node`, for each of those scales. The information required for doing so will be available in the ReFrame configuration file.

3.2.5 Time limit

Since the amount of tasks can vary substantially based on the available hardware in the system on which the portable test suite is used, parallel tests where the problem size is constant (used to measure *strong scaling* behaviour) may display strongly varying runtimes. Initially, we will simply set the time limit very liberally, i.e. simply impose a very high time limit. Apart from potential scheduling inefficiencies, there are few downsides to this approach. If needed, this can be refined with a very crude performance model (e.g. inverse scaling with the task count) as a first order improvement over a constant time limit. Note that the baseline would still have to be very liberal, as such performance models are notoriously inaccurate.

3.2.6 Performance references

Traditionally, performance reference values are hard-coded in the test (see for example the CSCS test suite [15]), which are clearly *very* system specific. Another challenge is that getting the correct reference values often requires a significant manual effort. ReFrame allows easy parametrization of tests, and will run a test for all combinations of those parameters. This means that for example a GROMACS test could easily have 150 variants: CPU vs GPU, for multiple scales (task counts), different GROMACS versions or installations, on multiple partitions, etc. Each variant has its own expected performance, which implies a lot of manual effort is required to collect reference performance metrics.

Typically, test implementers obtain their reference performance values by simply running the test suite a couple of times, and then basing the expected performance (and upper and lower bounds) based on those runs. The plan is to create a Python function in the portable test suite that can extract those numbers at run time from the performance

logs of previous runs. We will discuss with the ReFrame developers whether this is functionality that could be implemented into ReFrame itself, as this aspect is not specific to the portable test suite for the shared software stack.

While this is sufficient to identify performance *regressions* in testing, it does not provide a reference for the first runs on a new system. The only automated way in which this could be obtained is based on (known) references from other systems, combined with a performance model that takes into account the differences between the reference systems and the new system (e.g. in terms of CPU model, interconnect, etc). However, such performance models are typically unreliable, and creating a performance model for each test in the portable test suite would be a tremendous effort. In the end, we feel an expert human assessment, based on the performance reference values that are available for other systems, is the designated approach to assess performance on a new system.

3.3 Test suite hooks, utilities and constants

To implement the extensions proposed above, the portable test suite provides several hooks, utilities, and constants.

ReFrame has various execution stages when preparing a test (initialisation, setup, run, etc.), and ReFrame hooks allow functions to be executed right before and/or after these stages. The hooks implemented for the portable test suite are regular Python functions that are intended to be called as part of the ReFrame hook. Examples of currently implemented hooks in the portable test suite are:

- `assign_one_task_per_compute_unit`: takes care of setting `num_tasks`, `num_cpus_per_task`, and `num_gpus_per_node` based on what is configured for the current partition in the ReFrame configuration file. Compute units can be a full CPU, one CPU socket, or a GPU.
- `filter_valid_systems_by_device`: makes sure that e.g. a GPU-based test is only run if both the partition and software installation being used support GPUs.
- `set_modules`: allows overriding the name of the environment module to use for running the test;
- `set_tag_scale`: sets ReFrame tags for each of the scales (single core, two core, etc.) for which the test should be generated. This allows easily running a subset of scales (e.g. only single node tests) by passing the desired tag to ReFrame on command line.
- `check_custom_executable_opts`: allows command line overrides of the executable options
- `set_compact_process_binding`: binds processes to cores in a compact way, i.e. each process is bound to consecutive sets of cores.
- `set_compact_thread_binding`: binds threads in a compact way for multi-threaded software.

Some of these hooks facilitate implementing a portable test (e.g. `assign_one_task_per_compute_unit`). Others are meant to implement functionality that is commonly used in tests, to avoid code duplication (e.g. `set_compact_process_binding`). The plan is to extend these hooks as the need for either more portability arises, or when we see a lot of duplicated functionality across tests.

The utility functions provided by the portable test suite are more basic building blocks, and can be used in both tests and hooks. Examples are functions that support the module discovery according to a certain search pattern, checking if GPUs are present in the current partition, getting the number of GPUs for the current partition, etc.

The constants defined in the portable test suite standardize certain fields used in tests. For example, the way that a test can declare that certain feature (e.g. GPUs) are required is through free text strings. To standardize these values both in the portable test suite and the ReFrame configuration files, we define these free text strings as constants. Similarly, the *default* scales at which all tests get generated are defined as a constant.

4 Proof of concept for a portable test: GROMACS

The best way to discover how to make a portable test suite, is to try and implement a test, and try to run it on a range of different systems. The additional advantage is that this test can then serve as a blueprint for other tests to be developed in the future.

We decided to implement a test for GROMACS [18] as a proof of concept, since GROMACS is a very versatile application: it supports running on both CPUs and GPUs, supports a wide range of CPU and GPU architectures, scales well from a handful of cores to a large number of nodes, can run as pure MPI or hybrid MPI + OpenMP, etc. This made it an ideal candidate application for gaining experience in writing a portable test.

4.1 Test implementation

The full code of the EESSI test suite GROMACS test can be found in the appendix A. In this section, we will highlight certain parts to translate the ideas from Section 3 into concrete code.

First, the class variables are defined, which includes ReFrame parameter built-ins. ReFrame parameterises tests over the value of these parameters, and creates a test variant for each combination of parameters.

```
1 @rfm.simple_test
2 class GROMACS_EESSI(gromacs_check):
3     scale = parameter(SCALES.keys())
4     valid_prog_environs = ['default']
5     valid_systems = []
6     time_limit = '30m'
7     module_name = parameter(find_modules('GROMACS'))
```

The `scale` parameter shown above defines the set of scales at which this test is run, and is based on the `SCALES` constant defined in the portable test suite.

ReFrame requires that the `valid_prog_environs` variable is specified, but since this test does not have a separate compile step, we simply specify the default programming environment.

Initially, the `valid_systems` variable is set to a empty list; a non-empty value will be set later in the hooks.

A generic `time_limit` of 30 minutes has been set, which has shown to work across all system sizes we have encountered so far, even when using only a single core.

Finally, the `find_modules` function is called to discover all GROMACS modules available in the programming environment.

```
1 @run_after('init')
2 def run_after_init(self):
3     hooks.filter_valid_systems_by_device_type(self, required_device_type=self.nb_impl)
4     hooks.set_modules(self)
5     hooks.set_tag_scale(self)
```

The first initialisation hook `run_after_init` shown above makes sure that GPU-based variants of the test (i.e. those that put non-bonded interactions on the GPU by specifying `--nb=gpu` as argument to `gmx mdrun`) are only generated on systems that contain an NVIDIA GPU, and only if the GROMACS installation was built with support for running on NVIDIA GPUs. It also sets the `module` variable such that it can be overwritten from command line, and defines tags which allow easy selection of test scales from the command line. This is not required for test portability, but is there for convenience.

```
1 @run_after('init')
2 def set_tag_ci(self):
3     if self.benchmark_info[0] == 'HECBioSim/Crambin':
4         self.tags.add(TAGS['CI'])
```

The GROMACS test from the ReFrame test suite implements several different use cases. The next initialisation hook `set_tag_ci` shown above adds an additional `CI` tag to one of those: we do not need to run all use cases all the time. This tag allows us to easily filter down to one use case to run in a CI environment.

```
1 @run_after('setup')
2 def set_executable_opts(self):
3     num_default = 4 # normalized number of executable opts added by parent class (gromacs_check)
4     hooks.check_custom_executable_opts(self, num_default=num_default)
5     if not self.has_custom_executable_opts:
6         self.executable_opts += ['-dlb', 'yes', '-npme', '-1']
```

The next hook `set_executable_opts` allows for overriding executable options on the command line, which is again mainly done for convenience.

```

1 @run_after('setup')
2 def run_after_setup(self):
3     hooks.assign_one_task_per_compute_unit(test=self, compute_unit=self.nb_impl)

```

The `run_after_setup` hook sets the correct values for the `num_tasks`, `num_cpus_per_task`, and `num_gpus_per_node` variables, depending on whether this instance of the test class defines a CPU or GPU based test. For CPU based tests, this function set the number of tasks equal to the product of the number of nodes to be used for the test (provided by the `scales`) and the number of cores per node (provided by the ReFrame configuration file for the system on which the test runs). Similarly, for a GPU based test the number of tasks will be equal to the number of nodes multiplied by the number of GPUs per node available on the given system.

```

1 @run_after('setup')
2 def set_omp_num_threads(self):
3
4     if '-ntomp' in self.executable_opts:
5         omp_num_threads = self.executable_opts[self.executable_opts.index('-ntomp') + 1]
6     else:
7         omp_num_threads = self.num_cpus_per_task
8         self.executable_opts += ['-ntomp', str(omp_num_threads)]
9
10    self.env_vars['OMP_NUM_THREADS'] = omp_num_threads

```

Finally, the last hook `set_omp_num_threads` sets the `$OMP_NUM_THREADS` environment variable and `-ntomp` argument to GROMACS. This is quite particular to GROMACS: if both are set, GROMACS requires that these are *identical*. Since some systems set `$OMP_NUM_THREADS` based on the requested `cpus_per_task` in the job, this caused conflicts if `-ntomp` was set to a different value.

4.2 Example test runs: a demonstration of portability

The GROMACS test was run on a wide range of systems, selecting the HECBioSim/Crambin test case (with the CI tag), and selecting only the single node and two node runs (using `"1_node|2_nodes"` as tag value).

The following command line was used on all systems to start this (subset of) test(s), which demonstrates the portability of this test:

```
reframe --tag CI --tag "1_node|2_nodes" --run -n GROMACS
```

4.2.1 EuroHPC JU system Vega (IZUM)

A total of 4 tests was run on the EuroHPC JU system Vega, as there are 2 GROMACS modules in the 2023.06 version of the EESSI pilot repository that was used as shared software stack (GROMACS/2021.3-foss-2021a and GROMACS/2021.5-foss-2021b), and each of those was tested using a single node and with two nodes:

```

1 [ OK ] (1/4) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=2_nodes %module_name=GROMACS
2 /2020.4-foss-2020a-Python-3.8.2 /c3790f2a @vega:cpu+default
3 P: perf: 363.411 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)
4 [ OK ] (2/4) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=2_nodes %module_name=GROMACS
5 /2020.1-foss-2020a-Python-3.8.2 /5535abba @vega:cpu+default
6 P: perf: 357.646 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)
7 [ OK ] (3/4) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=1_node %module_name=GROMACS
8 /2020.4-foss-2020a-Python-3.8.2 /a108fe65 @vega:cpu+default
9 P: perf: 243.349 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)
10 [ OK ] (4/4) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=1_node %module_name=GROMACS
11 /2020.1-foss-2020a-Python-3.8.2 /695f354c @vega:cpu+default
12 P: perf: 246.27 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)

```

On Vega, all four GROMACS tests passed, and the performance metric (the amount of nanoseconds that GROMACS would be able to simulate in a day of simulation) is reported in the output.

4.2.2 EuroHPC JU system Karolina (IT4I)

A total of 4 tests was run on the EuroHPC JU system Karolina, as there are 2 GROMACS modules in the 2023.06 version of the EESSI pilot repository that was used as shared software stack (GROMACS/2021.3-foss-2021a and GROMACS/2021.5-foss-2021b), and each of those was tested using a single node and with two nodes:

```

1 [ OK ] (1/4) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=2_nodes %module_name=
  GROMACS/2021.5-foss-2021b /e55d7f40 @karolina:qcpu+default
2 P: perf: 482.549 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)
3 [ OK ] (2/4) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=2_nodes %module_name=
  GROMACS/2021.3-foss-2021a /d597cff4 @karolina:qcpu+default
4 P: perf: 471.961 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)
5 [ OK ] (3/4) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=1_node %module_name=GROMACS
  /2021.5-foss-2021b /ada124e7 @karolina:qcpu+default
6 P: perf: 302.859 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)
7 [ OK ] (4/4) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=1_node %module_name=GROMACS
  /2021.3-foss-2021a /b8c761ef @karolina:qcpu+default
8 P: perf: 300.519 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)

```

On Karolina, all four GROMACS tests passed, and the performance metric (the amount of nanoseconds that GROMACS would be able to simulate in a day of simulation) is reported in the output.

4.2.3 Snellius (SURF)

A total of 8 tests was run as the Snellius supercomputer operated by SURE, as there are 2 GROMACS modules in the 2023.06 version of the EESSI pilot repository that was used as shared software stack ((GROMACS/2021.3-foss-2021a and GROMACS/2021.5-foss-2021b), each of those was tested on a single node and with two nodes, and on two partitions (rome and genoa) which were defined in the ReFrame configuration file for Snellius:

```

1 [ FAIL ] (1/8) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=2_nodes %module_name=
  GROMACS/2021.5-foss-2021b /e55d7f40 @snellius:genoa+default
2 ==> test failed during 'sanity': test staged in '/scratch-shared/casparl/reframe_output/staging/snellius/genoa/
  default/GROMACS_EESSI_e55d7f40'
3 [ FAIL ] (2/8) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=2_nodes %module_name=
  GROMACS/2021.3-foss-2021a /d597cff4 @snellius:genoa+default
4 ==> test failed during 'sanity': test staged in '/scratch-shared/casparl/reframe_output/staging/snellius/genoa/
  default/GROMACS_EESSI_d597cff4'
5 [ FAIL ] (3/8) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=1_node %module_name=GROMACS
  /2021.5-foss-2021b /ada124e7 @snellius:genoa+default
6 ==> test failed during 'sanity': test staged in '/scratch-shared/casparl/reframe_output/staging/snellius/genoa/
  default/GROMACS_EESSI_ada124e7'
7 [ OK ] (4/8) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=1_node %module_name=GROMACS
  /2021.3-foss-2021a /b8c761ef @snellius:genoa+default
8 P: perf: 259.054 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)
9 [ OK ] (5/8) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=1_node %module_name=GROMACS
  /2021.3-foss-2021a /b8c761ef @snellius:rome+default
10 P: perf: 352.438 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)
11 [ OK ] (6/8) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=1_node %module_name=GROMACS
  /2021.5-foss-2021b /ada124e7 @snellius:rome+default
12 P: perf: 385.294 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)
13 [ OK ] (7/8) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=2_nodes %module_name=
  GROMACS/2021.5-foss-2021b /e55d7f40 @snellius:rome+default
14 P: perf: 478.883 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)
15 [ OK ] (8/8) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=2_nodes %module_name=
  GROMACS/2021.3-foss-2021a /d597cff4 @snellius:rome+default
16 P: perf: 471.182 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)

```

We see a couple of failures, each of them failing with:

```

1 [1700063935.874488] [tcn677:337956:0] ib_iface.c:1673 UCX ERROR Invalid active_speed on mlx5_2:1: 128

```

The reason for this is that the UCX version used by this GROMACS installation in the shared software stack is too old for the High Data Rate (HDR) interconnect in the Genoa partition of Snellius. The test suite correctly identifies that this particular module is not functional on this specific system / partition, as intended.

4.2.4 AWS Magic Castle

The test suite was also run on a Slurm cluster in AWS that was created using Magic Castle [19], which includes nodes for all eight CPU microarchitectures that are supported by version 2023.06 of the EESSI pilot repository that serves as a shared software stack. At the time of running the test suite, there was an issue with the Slurm configuration of this cluster for some of the node types. Hence, we limited the experiment to only use a limited, but representative, set of CPU architectures: AMD Rome (Zen 3), Intel Skylake, and ARM Graviton 2 (Neoverse N1).

As a result, a total of 12 tests was run: as there are two GROMACS modules (in the 2023.06 version of the EESSI pilot repository), at two scales (single node and two nodes), on a total of 3 CPU architectures. All nodes in this cluster run on virtual machines with 16 cores each.

```
1 [ OK ] ( 1/12) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=2_nodes %module_name=
2 GROMACS/2021.5-foss-2021b /e55d7f40 @Magic_Castle:x86_64-zen3-16c-30gb+default
3 P: perf: 97.176 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)
4 [ OK ] ( 2/12) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=2_nodes %module_name=
5 GROMACS/2021.5-foss-2021b /e55d7f40 @Magic_Castle:x86_64-skylake-16c-30gb+default
6 P: perf: 85.216 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)
7 [ OK ] ( 3/12) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=2_nodes %module_name=
8 GROMACS/2021.5-foss-2021b /e55d7f40 @Magic_Castle:aarch64-neoverse-N1-16c-32gb+default
9 P: perf: 49.242 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)
10 [ OK ] ( 4/12) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=2_nodes %module_name=
11 GROMACS/2021.3-foss-2021a /d597cff4 @Magic_Castle:x86_64-zen3-16c-30gb+default
12 P: perf: 97.106 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)
13 [ OK ] ( 5/12) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=2_nodes %module_name=
14 GROMACS/2021.3-foss-2021a /d597cff4 @Magic_Castle:x86_64-skylake-16c-30gb+default
15 P: perf: 84.451 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)
16 [ OK ] ( 6/12) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=1_node %module_name=
17 GROMACS/2021.5-foss-2021b /ada124e7 @Magic_Castle:x86_64-zen3-16c-30gb+default
18 P: perf: 65.176 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)
19 [ OK ] ( 7/12) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=1_node %module_name=
20 GROMACS/2021.3-foss-2021a /b8c761ef @Magic_Castle:x86_64-zen3-16c-30gb+default
21 P: perf: 64.965 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)
22 [ OK ] ( 8/12) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=2_nodes %module_name=
23 GROMACS/2021.3-foss-2021a /d597cff4 @Magic_Castle:aarch64-neoverse-N1-16c-32gb+default
24 P: perf: 50.757 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)
25 [ OK ] ( 9/12) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=1_node %module_name=
26 GROMACS/2021.5-foss-2021b /ada124e7 @Magic_Castle:x86_64-skylake-16c-30gb+default
27 P: perf: 62.533 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)
28 [ OK ] (10/12) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=1_node %module_name=
29 GROMACS/2021.3-foss-2021a /b8c761ef @Magic_Castle:x86_64-skylake-16c-30gb+default
30 P: perf: 61.361 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)
31 [ OK ] (11/12) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=1_node %module_name=
32 GROMACS/2021.5-foss-2021b /ada124e7 @Magic_Castle:aarch64-neoverse-N1-16c-32gb+default
33 P: perf: 40.479 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)
34 [ OK ] (12/12) GROMACS_EESSI %benchmark_info=HECBioSim/Crambin %nb_impl=cpu %scale=1_node %module_name=
35 GROMACS/2021.3-foss-2021a /b8c761ef @Magic_Castle:aarch64-neoverse-N1-16c-32gb+default
36 P: perf: 41.663 ns/day (r:0, l:None, u:None)
```

Here we observe that all 12 test variants pass, exhibiting the portability of the GROMACS test that serves as a blueprint for tests included in the portable test suite.

5 Conclusion and outlook

In this report, we discussed different levels and types of testing that are relevant for testing the shared software stack that is being developed in Task 1.1. We have presented the challenges in writing a portable test suite, and outlined a plan on how to write portable tests using ReFrame.

We presented a proof of concept for how to write a fully portable test, using GROMACS as a test case. This test can serve as a blueprint for implementing additional tests in the portable test suite. The hooks and utilities that were developed for this test will also be useful when implementing other tests.

Checking application performance against a reference was not yet included in the proof of concept. However, we have formulated one possible approach, in which performance references are extracted from performance logs of prior runs. This allows for the detection of performance regressions, something that is essential in a CI/CD setting.

Exploring the feasibility of the proposed approach to check performance references will be one of the next steps. Furthermore, the coverage of the test suite will be expanded by adding tests for more software that is part of the shared software stack.

A The EESSI test suite GROMACS test

Here, we provide the Python code for the EESSI GROMACS test. Note that this code only functions in conjunction with the GROMACS test class defined in the ReFrame Test Library [14], as well as the hooks, constants and utility functions from the EESSI test suite.

The code is included here to illustrate what a fully portable test would look like, and how that relies on the EESSI test library hooks, constants and utility functions.

```

1 """
2 This module tests the binary 'gmx_mpi' in available modules containing substring 'GROMACS'.
3 Test input files are taken from https://www.hecbiosim.ac.uk/access-hpc/benchmarks,
4 as defined in the ReFrame test library,
5 see https://github.com/reframe-hpc/reframe/blob/develop/hpctestlib/sciapps/gromacs/benchmarks.py
6
7 ReFrame terminology:
8
9 "pipeline stages":
10 https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/regression_test_api.html#pipeline-hooks
11
12 "test parameter": a list of values, which will generate different test variants.
13 https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/regression_test_api.html#reframe.core.builtins.parameter
14
15 "test variant": a version of a test with a specific value for each test parameter
16 https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/regression_test_api.html#test-variants
17
18 "concrete test cases": all test combinations that will actually run:
19 - test variants
20 - valid system:partition+programming environment combinations
21 https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/tutorial_deps.html#listing-dependencies
22
23 Tests can be filtered by name, tag, programming environment, system, partition, or maintainer,
24 see https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/manpage.html#test-filtering
25
26 Hooks acting on all possible test combinations (before filtering) are called after the 'init' stage.
27 Hooks acting on concrete test cases (after filtering) are called after the 'setup' stage.
28
29 See also https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/pipeline.html
30 """
31
32 import reframe as rfm
33
34 from hpctestlib.sciapps.gromacs.benchmarks import gromacs_check
35
36 from eessi.testsuite import hooks
37 from eessi.testsuite.constants import SCALES, TAGS
38 from eessi.testsuite.utils import find_modules, log
39
40
41 @rfm.simple_test
42 class GROMACS_EESSI(gromacs_check):
43     scale = parameter(SCALES.keys())
44     valid_prog_environs = ['default']
45     valid_systems = []
46     time_limit = '30m'
47     module_name = parameter(find_modules('GROMACS'))
48
49     @run_after('init')
50     def run_after_init(self):
51         """Hooks to run after the init phase"""
52
53         # Make sure that GPU tests run in partitions that support running on a GPU,
54         # and that CPU-only tests run in partitions that support running CPU-only.
55         # Also support setting valid_systems on the cmd line.
56         hooks.filter_valid_systems_by_device_type(self, required_device_type=self.nb_impl)
57
58         # Support selecting modules on the cmd line.
59         hooks.set_modules(self)
60
61         # Support selecting scales on the cmd line via tags.
62         hooks.set_tag_scale(self)
63
64     @run_after('init')
65     def set_tag_ci(self):
66         """Set tag CI on smallest benchmark, so it can be selected on the cmd line via --tag CI"""
67         # Crambin input is smallest input (20K atoms), cfr. https://www.hecbiosim.ac.uk/access-hpc/benchmarks

```

```

68     if self.benchmark_info[0] == 'HECBioSim/Crambin':
69         self.tags.add(TAGS['CI'])
70         log(f'tags set to {self.tags}')
71
72     @run_after('setup')
73     def set_executable_opts(self):
74         """
75         Add extra executable_opts, unless specified via --setvar executable_opts=<x>
76         Set default executable_opts and support setting custom executable_opts on the cmd line.
77         """
78
79         num_default = 4 # normalized number of executable opts added by parent class (gromacs_check)
80         hooks.check_custom_executable_opts(self, num_default=num_default)
81         if not self.has_custom_executable_opts:
82             self.executable_opts += ['-dlb', 'yes', '-npme', '-1']
83             log(f'executable_opts set to {self.executable_opts}')
84
85     @run_after('setup')
86     def run_after_setup(self):
87         """Hooks to run after the setup phase"""
88
89         # Calculate default requested resources based on the scale:
90         # 1 task per CPU for CPU-only tests, 1 task per GPU for GPU tests.
91         # Also support setting the resources on the cmd line.
92         hooks.assign_one_task_per_compute_unit(test=self, compute_unit=self.nb_impl)
93
94     @run_after('setup')
95     def set_omp_num_threads(self):
96         """
97         Set number of OpenMP threads.
98         Set both OMP_NUM_THREADS and -ntomp explicitly to avoid conflicting values.
99         Set default number of OpenMP threads equal to number of CPUs per task.
100        Also support setting OpenMP threads on the cmd line via custom executable option '-ntomp'.
101        """
102
103        if '-ntomp' in self.executable_opts:
104            omp_num_threads = self.executable_opts[self.executable_opts.index('-ntomp') + 1]
105        else:
106            omp_num_threads = self.num_cpus_per_task
107            self.executable_opts += ['-ntomp', str(omp_num_threads)]
108            log(f'executable_opts set to {self.executable_opts}')
109
110        self.env_vars['OMP_NUM_THREADS'] = omp_num_threads
111        log(f'env_vars set to {self.env_vars}')

```

Acknowledgements

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References

Acronyms used

EESSI	European Environment for Scientific Software Installations
HPC	High Performance Computing
CI	Continuous Integration
OS	Operating System
CoE	Centre of Excellence
AWS	Amazon Web Services
EuroHPC JU	Euro High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking
MPI	Message Passing Interface
HDR	High Data Rate

URLs referenced

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<https://www.multixscale.eu> ... <https://www.multixscale.eu>
<https://www.multixscale.eu/deliverables> ... <https://www.multixscale.eu/deliverables>
Internal Project Management Link ... <https://github.com/multixscale/planning/issues/102>
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